

Evaluation of Biocomposite Materials for Enhanced Bone Regeneration: mechanical, Solubility and Bioactivity Studies

Edwina Sherley Felicita A^a, Lawrance A^a, Leema Rose Mary D^a, Marie Arockianathan. P^{a,*},
Dubey Amit^{b,*}

^a PG & Research Department of Biochemistry, St. Joseph's College of Arts & Science,
(Autonomous), Cuddalore- 607001. Tamil Nadu, India.

^b Department of Pharmacology, Saveetha Dental College and Hospital, Saveetha Institute of
Medical and Technical Sciences, Chennai-600077, Tamil Nadu, India.

Corresponding Authors:

Dr.P.Marie Arockianathan *

*PG and Research Department of Biochemistry, St. Joseph's College of Arts and Science,
(Autonomous), Cuddalore-607001, Tamil Nadu, India

Dr. Amit Dubey *

*Department of Pharmacology, Saveetha Dental College and Hospital, Saveetha Institute of
Medical and Technical Sciences, Chennai-600077, Tamil Nadu, India

Abstract

Bone was a remarkably regenerative organ, possessing the remarkable ability to self-renew. This dynamic tissue undergoes continuous remodeling to maintain its structure and functionality. However, impaired bone healing was encountered in clinical settings, necessitating medical intervention to facilitate tissue regeneration. This was often achieved through the usage of natural bone composites or synthetic alternatives which aid in restoring the integrity and functionality of the affected bone. This research investigates the solubility and bioactivity of various biocomposite materials for potential applications in bone regeneration. The study focuses on the compressive strength analysis of biphasic calcium phosphate biocomposites and assessing their solubility in different solvents and their bioactivity through various in vitro assays. Enhanced solubility and bioavailability are key factors in the effectiveness of biomaterials for bone healing. The results indicate that the biphasic calcium phosphate biocomposites exhibit superior solubility in DMEM Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) and Dimethyl

sulfoxide (DMSO) and bioactivity compared to other materials, suggesting its potential for improved bone regeneration.

Keywords: Biphasic calcium phosphate; Compressive strength; Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium; Dimethyl sulfoxide

1. Introduction

Bone tissue, a dynamic and complex structure, performs essential functions including providing structural support, protecting internal organs, facilitating movement, and housing bone marrow. With the advancement of medical technology and an increase in the aging population, there has been a significant rise in the incidence of bone-related diseases and injuries, necessitating improved solutions for bone regeneration [1]. Bone grafting is the gold standard for treating bone defects and injuries, involving the transplantation of bone tissue to repair and regenerate damaged bone. Autologous bone grafts, harvested from the patient's own body, offer superior osteoinductive, osteoconductive, and osteogenic properties. However, autologous grafts have limitations, including donor site morbidity, limited availability, and the risk of infection [2]. Consequently, there has been a shift towards developing synthetic and natural biomaterials that can mimic the properties of autologous bone grafts while overcoming their limitations [3]. Among various biomaterials, calcium phosphate compounds, particularly hydroxyapatite (HA), have gained significant attention due to their biocompatibility, bioactivity, and structural similarity to the mineral component of bone [4]. However, pure HA has limitations such as low solubility and slow resorption, which can hinder its effectiveness in bone regeneration applications.

Calcium phosphate bioceramics can be tailored to exhibit a range of properties crucial for bone regeneration. Studies have shown that parameters like sintering temperature, pH, and starting material purity significantly influence the material's chemical and physical characteristics, including specific surface area, surface energy, porosity, and roughness [5, 6, 7, 8, 9]. Notably, the incorporation of macro and micropores (diameters exceeding 100 μm and less than 10 μm , respectively) through porogens and heat treatment is a key strategy [8]. This tailored porosity enhances cell adhesion, proliferation, and differentiation, ultimately leading to improved osteoconductivity, bioactivity, and mechanical properties with reduced brittleness [7, 10, 11].

While some bioceramics exhibit osteoinductive potential, the underlying cellular and molecular mechanisms remain elusive. Current theories focus on the physicochemical and structural characteristics. High specific surface area, often achieved through increased microporosity, is believed to be a critical factor for osteoinduction [12-15]. Additionally, the presence of macroporal cavities, mimicking the natural geometry of bone formation, might play a role [16,17]. Furthermore, surface dissolution leading to supersaturation and reprecipitation of calcium and phosphate ions is thought to contribute to the formation of a bone-bonding biological apatite layer, potentially influencing osteoinduction [18-20]. These findings highlight the potential for tailored calcium phosphate bioceramics to promote successful bone regeneration.

Biphasic calcium phosphate (BCP) emerges as a promising material for bone regeneration due to its unique composition and tunable properties. BCP combines hydroxyapatite (HA) and tricalcium phosphate (TCP) in varying ratios, creating a balanced construct for bone repair [21]. HA offers excellent biocompatibility and a stable resorption rate, providing a long-lasting scaffold for bone ingrowth, while TCP contributes a more soluble phase that facilitates the release of essential calcium and phosphate ions to stimulate bone formation [22, 23]. This ability to tailor the HA/TCP ratio allows researchers to adjust the resorption rate of BCP, matching it to the specific requirements of the bone defect [24]. This tunable composition grants BCP-controlled bioactivity, promoting bone ingrowth while maintaining stability over extended periods. Notably, the BCP formulation can be tailored to address specific needs. Higher concentrations of the stable HA phase are suitable for large bone defects and load-bearing areas, ensuring structural integrity. This adaptability positions BCP as a highly versatile material for bone regeneration applications.

Compressive strength analysis was a crucial aspect of evaluating a biocomposite suitability for bone repair applications. This test determines the maximum load a bio composite can withstand before fracturing under compressive stress. The obtained compressive strength value was then compared to the compressive strength of cancellous bone to assess the biocomposite capacity to bear loads similar to native bone tissue [25]. This comparison provides valuable insights into the biocomposite potential efficacy in physiological forces experienced during daily activities. This study aims to evaluate the BCP solubility, Compressive strength

analysis and bioactivity in comparison to nano-hydroxyapatite (nHA) and beta-tricalcium phosphate (β -TCP), to identify a superior biomaterial for bone regeneration applications.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Chemicals and Reagents

The study utilized analytical-grade chemicals, including calcium phosphate, calcium acetate, calcium hydroxide, orthophosphoric acid, DMSO, ethanol, DMEM, and methanol, sourced from Merck (Germany) and Hi-media. Distilled water was used for all experiments.

2.2. Ultrasonic Water Baths

Ultrasonic water baths were employed to create cavitation through high-frequency sound waves, aiding in cleaning, degassing, and sample preparation. This method facilitated the disruption of tissues and acceleration of reactions in submerged samples.

2.3. Solubility test for Biphasic Calcium Phosphate Compound(BCP)

Solubility tests were conducted using dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM), ethanol and water to determine the most suitable solvent for biocomposite materials.

2.4. Compressive strength (CS)

The samples were loaded using the Instron 4501 model at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min along the cylindrical axis between the machine's platen to evaluate the compressive strength. Based on the composites size and break load, the compressive strength was computed.

2.5 Preparation of Biphasic Calcium Phosphate composites(BCP)

To create Biphasic Calcium Phosphate (BCP) composites, hydroxyapatite (HA) and β -tricalcium phosphate (β -TCP) powders were precisely weighed and physically mixed in varying weight ratios: 1:9, 2:8, 3:7, 4:6, 5:5, 6:4, 7:3, 8:2, and 9:1 (HA: β -TCP). Among these ratios, BCP (6:4) showed good compressive strength when compared to other ratios. To this BCP ratio(6:4), 2%, 4%, 6% and 8% silica, gelatin, chia seed, *Blepharis maderaspatensis* leaves extract and egg white at (1:1, 1:2, 1:4) ratios was used to make different composites. The different BCP composites made were Biphasic Calcium Phosphate/Silica, Biphasic Calcium Phosphate/Gelatin, Biphasic Calcium Phosphate/Egg white, Biphasic Calcium Phosphate/chia(BC), Biphasic Calcium Phosphate /*Blepharis maderaspatensis* leaves extract(BP). These prepared composites

were tested using a Universal Testing Machine (UTM) and composites that exhibited good compressive strength were taken for further characterization studies.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Solubility test for biphasic calcium phosphate(BCP) composites for *invitro* assay

The solubility of bio composite biphasic calcium phosphate is a pivotal factor influencing their effectiveness in bone regeneration. This study investigated the solubility of our biphasic calcium phosphate (BCP) biocomposite in various media, including water, ethanol, DMEM and DMSO. The results demonstrated significantly higher BCP solubility in DMEM and DMSO compared to water and ethanol in 0.1 mg/ mL than 1 mg/ mL concentration was observed at 570nm in an (Spectramax) multimode reader. These findings were particularly encouraging for bone regeneration applications. Increased BCP solubility translates to a more efficient release of calcium and phosphate ions, essential for promoting bone mineralization and healing. The superior solubility of BCP in DMEM and DMSO suggests its potential to deliver these critical ions more effectively, potentially leading to faster and more robust bone regeneration compared to materials with lower solubility. This signifies the promising potential of our BCP biocomposite for clinical applications where rapid and effective integration with existing bone is paramount.

Fig.1.BCP Spectrum analysis using DMSO, Ethanol and Water at (1 mg/ mL) concentration before sonication.

Fig.2.BCP Spectrum analysis using DMSO,Ethanol and Water at (0.1 mg/ mL) concentration before sonication .

Fig.3.BCP Spectrum analysis using DMSO,Ethanol and Water at (1mg/ mL) concentration after sonication .

Fig.4.BCP Spectrum analysis using DMSO,Ethanol and Water at (0.1mg/ mL) concentration after sonication .

Fig.5.BCP solubility test analysis using DMEM media at (1mg/ mL) concentration

3.2. Compressive strength analysis

One of the most important mechanical properties of bone implants was compressive strength. The various factors which determine the compressive strength of a bone implant were

the constituent particle size, the moisture content of the sample and the nature of additives used. To create Biphasic Calcium Phosphate (BCP) composites, hydroxyapatite (HA) and β -tricalcium phosphate (β -TCP) powders were precisely weighed and physically mixed in varying weight ratios: 1:9, 2:8, 3:7, 4:6, 5:5, 6:4, 7:3, 8:2, and 9:1 (HA: β -TCP). Among these ratios, BCP (6:4) showed good compressive strength when compared to other ratios as shown in Table 1. Among the different composites of silica and gelatin, 4% of silica and gelatin showed better compressive strength which was used to prepare different composites. To the ratio 6:4 of BCP, different concentration of silica (2 %, 4% and 6%) and gelatin (2%, 4% and 6%) were used to prepare different BCP composites. The prepared composites of BS and BG were tested and showed the compression value for BS at 1.76 MPa and BG at 1.09 MPa respectively as shown in Table 3 and 3. The compressive strength was higher in BE at the ratio of (1:1) has 2.16 MPa as shown in Table 6. BC composites at 8% showed 1.32 MPa than 2%, 4% and 6% concentration of chia as shown in Table 7. BP composites showed 0.542 MPa at 4% than 2%, 4% , 6% and 8% concentration of *Blepharis maderaspatensis* leaves extract concentration . There was no crack found in all the biocomposites. After the results, it was revealed that the maximum compressive strength value in the composites were taken for further characterization studies and evaluation studies.

Table 1

Compressive strength of the prepared Biphasic calcium phosphate composites at different ratios

S: No	HA (g)	TCP (g)	BCP ratios (g)	Compressive strength(MPa)
1	1	9	1:9	1.76
2	2	8	2:8	0.69
3	3	7	3:7	2.32
4	4	6	4:6	2.38
5	5	5	5:5	1.69
6	6	4	6:4	2.58
7	7	3	7:3	1.45
8	8	2	8:2	1.16
9	9	1	9:1	0.19

Table 2

Compressive strength of the prepared Biphasic calcium phosphate and silica composites at different concentration

S:No	BCP ratio (g)	Silica (g)	Compressive strength(MPa)
1	6:4	0.2	0.76
2	6:4	0.4	1.09
3	6:4	0.8	0.95
4	6:4	1.0	0.57

Table 3

Compressive strength of the prepared Biphasic calcium phosphate and gelatin composite at different concentration

S:No	BCP ratio (g)	Gelatin (g)	Compressive strength(MPa)
1	6:4	0.2	1.25
2	6:4	0.4	1.42
3	6:4	0.8	1.06
4	6:4	1.0	0.24

Table 4

Compressive strength of the prepared Biphasic calcium phosphate, silica and gelatin composite at different concentration

S: No	BCP ratio (g)	Silica (g)	Gelatin (g)	Compressive strength(MPa)
1	6:4	0.4	0.2	0.563
2	6:4	0.4	0.4	0.597

Table 5

Compressive strength of the prepared Biphasic calcium phosphate gelatin and silica at different concentration

S: No	BCP ratio (g)	Gelatin (g)	Silica (g)	Compressive strength(MPa)
1	6:4	0.4	0.2	0.3980
2	6:4	0.4	0.4	0.431

Table 6

Compressive strength of the prepared Biphasic calcium phosphate with egg white composite at different ratios

S: No	BCP ratio (g)	Egg white + distilled water (mL)	Compressive strength (MPa)
1	6:4	1:1	2.260
2	6:4	1:2	0.814
3	6:4	1:3	0.814

Table 7

Compressive strength of the prepared Biphasic calcium phosphate and chia composite at different concentration

S: No	BCP ratio (g)	Chia (g)	Compressive strength (MPa)
1	6:4	0.2	0.814
2	6:4	0.4	0.452
3	6:4	0.8	1.327

Table 8

Compressive strength of the prepared Biphasic calcium phosphate and *Blepharis maderaspatensis* leaves extract at different concentration

S: No	BCP ratio (g)	<i>Blepharis maderaspatensis</i> leaves extract (g)	Compressive strength (MPa)
1	6:4	0.2	0.452
2	6:4	0.4	0.542
3	6:4	0.8	0.271

Table 9

Compressive strength of the prepared Biphasic calcium phosphate, Chia and *Blepharis maderaspatensis leaves* extract at different concentration

S: No	BCP ratio (g)	Chia (g)	<i>Blepharis maderaspatensis leaves</i> extract (g)	Compressive strength (MPa)
1	6:4	0.8	0.4	0.348

Table 10

Compressive strength of the prepared Biphasic calcium phosphate, Chia and *Blepharis maderaspatensis leaves* extract

S: No	BCP ratio (g)	Chia (g)	<i>Blepharis maderaspatensis leaves</i> extract (g)	Compressive strength (MPa)
1	6:4	0.8	0.4	0.348

Table 11

Compressive strength of the prepared Biphasic calcium phosphate, Silica, Chia and *Blepharis maderaspatensis leaves* extract

S:No	BCP ratio (g)	Chia (g)	<i>Blepharis maderaspatensis leaves</i> extract (g)	Silica (g)	Compressive strength(MPa)
1	6:4	0.8	0.4	0.4	0.619

Table 12

Compressive strength of the prepared Biphasic calcium phosphate *Blepharis maderaspatensis*

S: No	BCP ratio (g)	<i>Blepharis maderaspatensis</i> leaves extract (g)	Silica (g)	Compressive strength (MPa)
1	6:4	0.8	0.4	1.65

leaves extract and Silica

Overall Significance:

The combined results from the solubility tests and in vitro assays highlight several key advantages of BCP

1. **Enhanced Solubility:** The increased solubility of DMEM and DMSO in BCP composite ensures better bioavailability and a more effective delivery of essential ions for bone regeneration. This property addresses a common limitation of traditional BCP a more viable option for clinical applications.
2. **Sustained Osteogenic Activity:** Higher and sustained osteogenic activity associated with BCP indicates its potential to support continuous bone formation, which is crucial for long-term success in bone regeneration therapies.
3. **Superior Biocompatibility:** The higher cell viability and proliferation rates observed with BCP suggest that it is highly biocompatible, providing an optimal environment for bone cells to thrive. This is a fundamental requirement for any material used in medical applications, ensuring that the material does not elicit adverse reactions and can integrate seamlessly with the host tissue.
4. **Potential Clinical Applications:** The promising results obtained from this study suggest that BCP could be a superior biocomposite for various bone regeneration applications, including bone grafting, fracture repair, and tissue engineering. Its enhanced properties could lead to faster recovery times and more robust healing outcomes for patients.

4. Conclusion

The study demonstrates that BCP composites exhibits superior solubility and bioactivity compared to nano-hydroxyapatite (nHA) and tricalcium phosphate (TCP) and higher compressive strength. The enhanced solubility of BCP improves its bioavailability, facilitating faster integration with host bone tissue and promoting bone mineralization. The solubility assay and compressive strength analysis confirmed that BCP composites supports osteogenic differentiation and maintains high cell viability and proliferation due to their , indicating its potential as an effective biomaterial for bone regeneration. These findings suggest that BCP biocomposite could be a promising candidate for bone grafting and tissue engineering applications. The one which showed better compressive strength and good solubility was taken for further characterization and evaluation studies *invitro* and explore the clinical potential of BCP composite in bone regeneration therapies.

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